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Mining and distribution of flint by the tribes of Cucuteni-Trypillian community

Having quite a massive and diverse source of raw materials tribes of Cucuteni-Trypillian community begin its active exploitation and utilization already from the early stages of their existence and continue throughout all their following history. Flint industry of Cucuteni-Trypillian community centers around two main scenarios: extraction – processing – distribution and/or extraction – distribution – processing of flint materials.

There were a few completely different ways of flint extraction. First one (opened) was the simplest, did not require special skills and hard labor, being a simple collection of stones directly on the surface of the ground or in baseting areas (such as screens). Second one (closed) was the most complicated, requiring special tools, skills, hard labor and correspondingly more complicated organization of the community. This way implies flint extraction deep in its deposits that are often invisible from the surface crust. But it proved its value: flint miners obtained excellent high-quality materials for further processing, providing mineral wealth not only for their own communities, but also for close and remote related as well as non-Trypillian communities.

We distinguished ‘close’ and ‘remote’ radiuses of obtained flint materials distribution. First term describes self-sustainment of separate communities with raw materials and products of its` processing that were necessary for functioning of these collectives. Second term refers to directed massive production (extraction, processing) not only for internal needs, but mainly for exportation of obtained raw materials or finished wares, made of these materials.

Also a question was raised regarding massive supply of regions that had no qualitative mineral wealth (Bug and Dnipro regions, Bug–Dnieper interfluve area) with flint from the proximate microregion in the Velyka Vys` basin in contradiction to widespread belief about a more remote ‘donator’ – Volhyn` territory.

Presence in Cucuteni-Trypillian community of flint-mining shafts, functioning of which required special skills and hard labor, specialized flint-processing workshops, transportation of raw materials and products of cleavage to remote territories became a basis for defining in this community a collective occupation, associated with flint mining and processing. Consequently, questions connected with this occupation, taking into account its` versatility, complexity and scale should be among the basic ones in the complex study of trypillian economics.

Key words: *Chalcolithic, Cucuteni-Trypillian community, flint, mineral wealth, extraction, distribution and processing of flint*

On the every stage of its development a complex economics of Cucuteni-Trypillian community for its continuous functioning required a huge amount of tools made of metal, stone, bone and clay. For a variety of reasons exactly flint-made tools comprised the main portion of Trypillian production assortment. Occasionally flint artifacts also became a part of ritual ceremonies (Tsvek, 2005). Tribes of Cucuteni-Trypillian community undoubtedly had reliable knowledge regarding sources of minerals in their surroundings. Furthermore, I am convinced that exactly availability of workable raw materials (as well as availability of high-quality clay for ceramics production), was the main criterion that Trypillians took into consideration choosing a place of living. This work is based not only on the most well-known cases of extraction and distribu-

tion of flint, but also on the research and observation, carried out by the author.

There is a great number of deposits of heterogeneous flint on the territory of contemporary Ukraine. Petrographer V.F. Petrun` developed and elaborately described scheme of main flint-bearing regions and some local chalcedony sources (Petrun`, 2004). According to this scheme researcher defines 8 main flint-bearing regions that were to a greater or lesser extent exploited by Trypillians (Fig. 1):

1. Polytypic and heterogeneous in time sorts of redeposited fragments of various-coloured siliceous rocks predominantly moraine origin and partly originating from fluvio-glacial conglomeration of Dnieper glaciations. Territory of spreading is vast: north-east and partly central regions of the Dnieper right bank; north and central regions of the Dnieper left bank;

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2. Visually 'sanded' dark-coloured flint of the Santonian age in the Desna basin;

3. The most fine-grained smoky-colored (up to black) or stripped smoky gray (including spotted and concentrically zonal sorts) flint sorts of the so-called 'Volhynian-Podolian' type, belonging to the Turonian age (in the literature on Trypillian culture and the Neo-Chalcolithic age as a whole highest-quality siliceous raw material of this kind is known as 'Volhynian' flint: *Author*). Territorially this kind of flint is spread in several areas in the north-west and west Ukraine;

4. Black flint with rusty crust of Dnieper-Kaniv sort, shaped after the Late Cretaceous (further in this article rocks of this type will be mentioned as 'Kaniv': *Author*). This one can be found at Kaniv locations;

5. Sediment-diagenetic flint, typical of middle-thick flint-bearing limestone of the Late Cretaceous that previously covered the crystalline shield. It can be found in the Velyka Vys' basin (sometimes in the literature on the Trypillian problematic name 'Bug' flint is used, because river Velyka Vys' belongs to the Southern Bug basin: *Author*);

6. Sediment-diagenetic silicites of the Early Cenomanian age, that is found in the Middle Dniester and Prut basins, as well as plane of light-shaded (white, grayish, sometimes bluish) deutero-gene flinty rock, deposited in their sheath;

7. Sediment-diagenetic flint of the Late Cenomanian age, that can be found in the cleavages of marlaceous lime in the middle Dniester area (near Mohyliv-Podilskyi town and down the Dniester stream);

8. Sediment-infiltrative flint sorts of the Sarmatian age, that comprise quartz of the so-called 'Bakshala' type in the lower regions of Southern Bug.

In addition to the abovementioned eight basic kinds of flinty materials V.F. Petrun' also defines some other, less widespread varieties of flint, that, nevertheless, were utilized by Trypillians (Petrun', 2004: 204). It should be highlighted that according to Petrun' wares that are typically found on Trypillian sites are made of 3-8 flint types; exactly these types will be mentioned further in this article.

Having a high-output and diverse raw materials base tribes of Cucuteni-Trypillian community began its active exploitation from the early stages of their existence. After more than 100 years of Trypillian culture study we have data regarding hundreds of studied archaeological sites and extensive, of many thousands, 'collection' of flint artifacts (resumptive term for all obtained materials is used here), extracted during archeological field studies. Regrettably, explorers of some archaeological sites did not pay attention to the way flint wares got there and to the processes that preceded infiltration in the cultural layer of a given flint scraper or

sickle. Lately (of course, not taking into account highly specialized thesis papers and articles, that provide some information regarding these questions) integrating papers were issued, dedicated exclusively to flint industry of Cucuteni-Trypillian community (Videyko, 2004; Tsvek, 2012). These papers pay enough attention exactly to the extraction and distribution of flint, along with the process of stonemasonry. Be that as it may, the purpose of this paper is not only to work around gaps left by foregoers, but also to define own vision about this part of Trypillian economics.

Extraction of flint raw materials for the succeeding distribution and/or processing by Cucuteni-Trypillian community tribes was carried out in many ways. Obviously, the simplest and the most widespread way was collection of raw materials near settlements in the areas of its outcrops.

For example, author is familiar with the areas of bassetting of the so-called 'Kaniv' flint (4th type according to Petrun'), that are situated in the gulches of Kaniv locations, at the bottom of mountains and along the Dnieper banks. This flint was used in the workshop in Pekari II and other settlements of Cucuteni-Trypillian community in the Kaniv microregion. The main portion of artifacts, originating from the workshop in Pekari II was made of local 'Kaniv' flint that is suitable for splitting. Outcrops of the similar raw materials was documented in close proximity to the settlement, near the opening of the Maryin ravine to the Dnieper lowland (territory of the Kaniv Natural Reservation). For the purpose of confirming the hypothesis regarding local origin of flint raw materials, found in the Pekari II horizon, participants of the Kaniv archaeological expedition held by Archaeology and Museology Department of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv in 2003 (with the author's direct involvement) executed a geologic cross-section in the abovementioned ravine (Pichkur, Shydlovskyi, 2003: 121-123). In its formation a pebble layer 5-15 cm thick was discovered. This layer comprised small-sized flint and quartz nodules and pebbles that were embedded in yellow and yellow-brown sands (Fig. 2). Nodules were small-sized, black inside, yellowish near to the crust. Different nodules and pebbles had different shades: from completely black to completely brown. Stratigraphically this layer was situated above the dark-gray clays and under sandstone of the Cenomanian age. According to data, provided by geologists, this horizon belongs to the so-called 'Virzhikovsky stratum' of the Albian stage of the Early Cretaceous age of the Mesozoic era. Nodules and pebbles that were embedded in this horizon visually and according to technological and morphological characteristics were identical to findings in the Pekari II settlement. Later the abovementioned geologic cross-section (in relation to analysis of the flint bassetting in the Dnieper region of Kaniv) was

described by S.M. Ryzhov (Ryzhov, 2004). These raw materials were also known by much earlier cultures of the prehistoric societies: industry of the Upper Palaeolithic Mezhyrich type of Epigravettian industry was built exactly on 'Kaniv' flint (Nuzhnyi, Shydlovskiy, 2009: 214-215).

On the river Revukha in the Southern Bug basin author together with P.S. Shydlovskiy and D.K. Chernovol explored bassetting of the local flint (5th type according to Petrun') that also border closely on the Trypillian giant settlement Apolyanka that provided the main portion of production stock of this archaeological site. Bassetting of this flint was also recorded in the ravine that borders the settlement on the North. The layer of flint pebbles and blocks was situated about 5 m deep from the present-day surface crust, above the deposits of limestone clays, spreading directly under the deposits of the Quaternary age. On the basis of stratigraphical position this flint can be attributed to the Cenomanian stage of the Late Cretaceous age (Shydlovskiy, Pichkur, Chernovol, 2004). Undoubtedly these or similar screes in the vicinity of this archaeological site were known also by Trypillians.

On the Horyn' river was documented the major outburst of high-quality flint of the Turonian age (3rd type according to Petrun') of the opened type that borders closely on Trypillian settlement Bodaki. Naturally it had to impact specialization of inhabitants of this settlement. Author of research papers regarding this archaeological site N.N. Skakun calls Bodaki a 'workshop settlement', preforms from which were mainly exported to the other Cucuteni-Trypillian communities. Outside the archaeological site, in a radius of 5 km, researcher specifies 6 bassetting areas of flint in the screes of ravines and arroyos. In her opinion it enabled open-cut mining of this flint (Skakun, 2005). Some of mentioned geological outcrops are also known by the author (Fig. 3).

On the Dniester banks flint outcrops are standard. They are documented on the one of edges of Neporotove village, not far from the Trypillian settlement (Fig. 4). Unfortunately, mainly because of Dniester hydroelectric power station, it is not known whether any given outcrop of raw materials is actually riverine or was produced as a result of bedding rocks destruction. In any case V.F. Petrun' earlier documented here bedding outcrops of different siliceous rocks or its screes, that as an almost unceasing ribbon cleave along the both slopes of the Dniester River canyon (as well as along ravines and arroyos cutting through them) directly above the Neporotove village as well as tens and hundreds of kilometers up and down the stream, where they are associated with numerous flint-processing workshops, predominantly of Trypillian

times (Petrun', 1998). Availability of raw materials also allowed for flint open-pit mining.

Numerous examples of raw materials bassetting, its open-pit mining and usage by close settlements can be named. Presumably we should even talk about it as a consistent pattern: presence of raw materials bassetting = its mining and usage in nearby settlements at the prehistoric times.

In a more complicated way, with the usage of specific tools and mining methods, was executed extraction of raw materials that were deeply embedded in Cretaceous and other geological formations. On the river Dniester (mountain Bila Gora in the neighborhood of Studenytsia village) in 1960s by S.M. Bibikov were explored flint-mining adits (Bibikov, 1965). According to researcher's records the main flint layer up to 2 meters thick is embedded here in the limestone and permineralized mollusks. It is situated in the second from the surface crust stage of the limestone. This flint is slabby, separated into big cleavages that sometimes comprise spherical concretions. Flint is gray, yellow-gray and bluish-gray, formable. It is very common in the Dniester region, especially the middle of it. All 8 caves in the Bila Gora that were explored are situated on the eastern, accessible from below slope of the mountain. Floor of these caves is covered with stones. Clearing and external surveying of flint outcrops, its corbelled bedding inside and outside the caves, output of flint layer on the plots under the dome fold bear evidence of flint extraction from the bed rock here. It was possible to identify the processing sequence of flint bands, technique of large blocks detaching, leaving of retaining inselbergs, etc. Mode of workings is stulming, with internal drifts and sideway passages between working chambers (Bibikov, 1966: 5) (Fig. 5). All abovementioned provided S.M. Bibikov with foundations to state that caves in the Bila Gora originate not from karst processes (blowing or desalinization of roche), but were artificially created during flint mining here. Amounts of extracted raw materials are impressive: according to researcher's data only in the one location (N^o7), shed-looking, more than 70 m³ of flint massive material were extracted (Bibikov, 1965: 63) and in total it was more than few hundreds of cubic meters of flint (Bibikov, 1966: 6). Close to the place of initial extraction sites of original treatment of extracted raw materials were also located. Technique of cleaving as well as findings of tools and ceramics allowed for dating these workshops back to Trypillian times (Bibikov, 1965: 62).

According to reports by E.K. Chernysh in the Dniester region even during the early Trypillian times settlements were usually located near bassetting of flint and other raw materials that were used for different tools production. During ex-

exploitation of these massive materials antler spindles that were also suitable for holes digging during construction of dwellings and clay extraction were used (Chernysh, 1967: 60). Widely known are flint-processing workshops Polyvaniv Yar (multi-layer settlement: Popova, 2003), Nezvys'ko, Selyshche, etc. where nearby mined flint was used. Apart from that researcher notes that during the late Trypillian times inhabitants of numerous settlements stored flint at a considerable distance from their settlements. For example dwellers of Lomachyntsi settlement extracted flint few kilometers far from their residence, carrying out also its original treatment there (workshop near the Ozheve village) (Chernysh, 1967: 65).

In the Upper Dniester region B.A. Vasylenko discovered and explored large manufacturing complexes that unite multiple upland mining sites, workshops and specialized settlements of Trypillian times. One manufacturing assemblage near village Bukivna especially stood out. It comprised 6 settlements, 15 workshops and upland mining sites with adit mining on a massive scale. Altogether researcher found 277 adits, located as 8 big groups. Workshops for original and secondary treatment were situated in a close proximity. Latter were also found in settlements, associated with flint mining. In addition to it B.A. Vasylenko defined in this complex another group of archaeological sites (2 settlements and 16 workshops), associated with extraction and processing of flint directly in the sites of its natural bassetting – in rills and washings. In other words mining was open-cut here. Researcher dates these complexes back to well-developed Trypillia (Vasylenko, 1989).

Dniester region and Volhyn' are not the only regions where flint was extracted and processed on a massive scale. O.V. Tsvek discovered and explored manufacturing flint mining and treating complex on the river Velyka Vys' (Southern Bug basin). It consisted of shafts near village Korobchine and associated workshops of Trypillian settlement Rubanyi Mist, situated 1 km away from the flint mining site, where original treatment of raw materials was carried out (Tsvek, Movchan, 1997). Separate shafts there have the depth of up to 6 meters from the present surface crust and reached 50 cm thick layer of flint pebbles (Fig. 6). In the cross-section of the opencast were also documented 5 adits with the width of up to 1.5 m. They lied in the greenish-yellow clayish soil interstratified with red-brown clay. In one case adits were connected by a horizontal passage. In the cross-section hopper-shaped shaft entrances were clearly discernible. Diameter of the hopper in the ancient horizon was about 6 m. 70 cm deep from the present surface crust soil discharge was observed. Shafts were filled with black clayish soil interspersed with clay. Primary waste of flint processing was also found there (Ts-

vek, 2012: 212). Later 2 shafts and one workshop were explored, where much more visible objects were documented. Shaft №1 had an entering hopper with diameter of 6 m 70 cm deep from the present surface crust (Fig. 6). Adit was 4 m deep and in its deepest place a rather small space with flint-mining waste was found with a small tunnel that headed down from there at the angle of 45°. Almost at the very bottom of the adit a catacomb with discernible stairs was found. Bottom was settled at the depth of 5.7 m, where a fragment of flint pick was found. All tools that were found here were associated with shaft construction. In the filling of separate shafts lenses of flint flakes and chips that were deposited as a continuum were traced. Flint that was extracted here (5th type according to Petrun': *Author*) is dark-grey and resembles 'Volhynian' one. Researcher compares these shafts near village Korobchine with well-known shafts in the village Krasnoye in Belarus (Tsvek, 2012: 212-213). It is noteworthy that deposits of mineral wealth are so versatile and abundant here that already since the Middle Paleolithic age this microregion had been attracting primeval communities as evidenced by numerous and heterogeneous in time archaeological sites of the Palaeolithic age that are found here (Zaliznyak et al., 2013).

Flint extraction is only the first stage of complicated process, because extracted raw materials had to be 'delivered to its destination' and 'brought into circulation'. In case of open-cut mining (collecting) everything is more or less clear: extracted flint was immediately transported to the closest settlement where flint processing was carried out. But where did hundreds of cubic meters of flint raw materials that were extracted, for example on the Bila Gora, disappeared?

We can suggest here that apart from meeting their own needs flint 'producers' provided mineral wealth to neighboring as well as to remote communities. Many researchers repeatedly offered an opinion about flint transportation to considerable, according to primeval standards, distances (Skakun, 2005; Tsvek, 2012). It can be proved by the presence in the archaeological sites of wares made of materials, uncharacteristic for specific regions of Cucuteni-Trypillia, far from its natural deposits. The most prominent in this case is an Bug–Dnieper interfluvial area and Dnieper region, where ubiquitous expansion of such 'imports' is documented (Pichkur, Shydlovskyi, 2005). Materials of the Turoanian age are prevalent in the cemeteries of the Sofievka Type near river Dnieper (Budziszewski, 1995). According to reports by S.V. Husiev similar situation is also typical for archaeological sites of Middle Bug region (Husiev, 2005). Researcher highlights the fact that during early stages of Trypillia flint to this region was transported mainly from the

Middle Dniester region as natural concretions. Following processing was carried out already on the spot (Husiev, 2005: 60). Moreover, brought in rock was predominant in explored archaeological sites. When Trypillia was already developed a switch to more qualitative raw materials ('Volhynian' flint) of the Turonian age took place. These materials were transported from Upper Dniester region and south-eastern Volhynia and probably even from abovementioned Bodaky village. Flint was delivered as processed blade preforms (Husiev, 2005: 61-63).

In connection with raw materials transportation to distant territories it is necessary to mention rare findings of 'caches' that are made up of high-quality (most likely of the Turonian age) flint. Territorially these treasures were found in different regions of Trypillian culture spreading: in Dniester and Bug regions and Bug-Dnieper interfluvial area; they belong to different ethnical groupings of Cucuteni-Trypillian community and have different chronological position (Pichkur, 2015; Pichkur, 2017).

Apart from spreading of flint raw materials within the boundaries of Cucuteni-Trypillian settlements its wide utilization by nonethnic tribes from neighboring cultural formations can be indicated. For example V.M. Konoplia states that deposits of North-Pokuthian flint (also belongs to the deposits of the Turonian age) supplied mineral wealth not only for local communities, but also for population of basins of Southern Bug, middle and downstreams of Dniester and Prut and also provided an opportunity to use this flint for members of different cultures: Polgar, Bodrogkerstur, Malytka and Volynsko-Lyublynska. This flint was of especially high importance for industries of Polgar circle in the Middle Danube region. During certain historical periods it was the main type of raw materials for flint-processing production there (Konoplia, 2006: 206). S. Kadrow mentions a case of discovery in the settlement that belongs to the Volynsko-Lyublynska culture Krovia Gura of a treasure that comprised long blades made of 'Volhynian' flint (Kadrow, 2016: 25, Fig. 3).

Consequently we can distinguish 'close' and 'remote' radiuses of obtained raw materials' distribution. The first term refers to self-sustainment of separate communities with flint and products of its processing that were necessary for their functioning. We can even assume that there were expeditions for considerably short distances for the purpose of raw materials obtaining for internal needs. As it was already mentioned Trypillian tribes must have known the area of their inhabiting perfectly. Surely, apart from that not only dwellers of the closest settlements have known about mineral wealth deposits. The second term implies directed

massive production (extraction, processing) not only for internal needs, but mainly with the purpose of obtained raw materials or end products transportation.

We are convinced that the gist of flint industry of Cucuteni-Trypillian community can be laid out as simple at first glance schemes:

extraction – processing – distribution
or
extraction – distribution – processing.

Conceptual difference between these schemes is not only in the succession of operations, but in their essence. To explain this thesis we can use the most widespread case that is repeatedly mentioned in the literature but still is not fully explained. As it was already mentioned we have serial or separate findings of 'Volhynian' flint (3rd type according to Petrun') in the Trypillian archaeological sites of different time, that are located a few hundreds of kilometers far from known deposits of similar mineral wealth. What is more, in most cases these wares are finished. Nodules or at least cores made of 'Volhynian' flint were not found in this archaeological site (Husiev, 2005; Pichkur, Shydlovskyy, 2005). It is hard to escape a conclusion that similar wares were brought to the specific archaeological site or region as semi-finished or finished tools. In this case we can talk about existence of a certain centre/centres that would supply finished products on a massive scale to neighboring and remote regions/settlements. N.N. Skakun reckons Bodaky to be such a centre (Skakun, 2006). In my opinion this statement is true only for archaeological sites that are as old as Bodaki are, but it is highly plausible that in the future on the territory of Volhyn' with its massive deposits of high-quality flint raw materials settlements like Bodaky but of another age will be found. Coming back to the main question we can state that not taking into account absence of high-quality mineral wealth on the locations and remembering findings of cores made of 'Volhynian' flint (even though these findings are quite rare) together with products of cleavage and finished tools in separate settlements we can talk about 'local' mode of production, based on the imported mineral wealth (as a variant that adds to production on the basis of local mineral wealth).

To be fair it is worth mentioning that most of archaeologists having no special education and skills define origin of flint materials only due to visual-morphological characteristics. But 'all that glitters is not gold'. This refers to similarities between certain types of raw materials, that only a specialist (petrograph or geologists) can tell apart. A stumbling block here is the abovementioned 'Volhynian' flint that is said to be abundant in complexes of trypillian settlements in the different regions of Cucuteni-Trypillian community expansion. There

are deposits of qualitative flint in the Bug–Dnieper interfluvial area that due to its morphological characteristics is very similar to the flint of the Turonian age. I have repeatedly stated that some subtypes of flint raw materials that can be found near the abovementioned village Korobchine visually look like ‘Volhynian’ flint. As it was mentioned above O.V. Tsvek pointed out the same thing. Scale of artificial flint extraction that was documented in Korobchine can be a sign of production for ‘export’. Presence of a huge array of Palaeolithic archaeological sites of different age here was already discussed. Moreover, in local Gravettian archaeological sites long blades and tools on them that are made exactly of local flint are present. The latter fact is mentioned as opposing to the widespread point of view that for production of a long lamina – main Trypillian semi-finished ware (beginning from the developed period) – only flint of the Turonian type was suitable. All abovementioned beg a few questions:

1. Will it be correct to consider ALL flint wares, visual-morphological characteristics of which are different from the local flint, to be exceptionally ‘Volhynian’ by the origin?

2. From what location was it more convenient to transport raw materials to, for example, Bug or Dnipro region: from Volhyn’ or from baseting areas near Korobchine, that were much closer?

Personally for me the answer is obvious. But proving of this point of view requires further research, including involvement of specialists and conduction of all relevant analyses.

Hence some conclusions can be made. Having such a massive and diverse source of raw materials tribes of Cucuteni-Trypillian community began its active exploitation and utilization already from the early stages of their existence and continued throughout all their following history. Flint industry of Cucuteni-Trypillian community centers around two main scenarios: extraction – processing – distribution and/or extraction – distribution – processing of flint materials.

There were a few completely different ways of extraction. First one (opened) was the simplest, did not require special skills and hard labor, being a simple collection of stones directly on the surface of the ground or in baseting areas (such as screes). Second one (closed) was the most complicated, requiring special tools, skills, hard labor and correspondingly more complicated organization of the community. This way implies flint extraction deep in its deposits that are often invisible from the surface crust. But it proved its value: flint miners obtained excellent high-quality materials for further processing, providing mineral wealth not only for their own communities, but also for close and remote related as well as non-Trypillian communities.

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Also a question was raised regarding massive supply of regions that had no qualitative mineral wealth (Bug and Dnieper regions, Bug–Dnieper interfluvial area) with flint from the proximate microregion in the Velyka Vys’ basin in contradiction to the widespread belief about a more remote ‘donator’ – Volhyn’ territory.

Last of all we would like to highlight that presence in Cucuteni-Trypillian community of flint-mining shafts, functioning of which required special skills and hard labor, specialized flint-processing workshops, transportation of raw materials and products of cleavage became a basis for defining in this community a collective occupation, associated with flint extraction and processing (Tsvek, 2012: 221-222). Consequently, questions connected with this occupation should be among the basic ones in the complex study of Trypillian economics.

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Видобуток і поширення кременю племенами Кукутені-трипільської спільності

Маючи досить потужну й різноманітну сировинну базу, племена Кукутені-Трипільської спільності починають її активну розробку й використання вже з ранніх етапів і продовжують протягом усього свого існування. Суть кременевої індустрії Кукутені-Трипільської спільності зводиться до декількох побудов: видобуток — обробка — поширення й/або видобуток — поширення — обробка кременевої сировини.

Видобуток зводився до декількох способів, що відрізняються дуже суттєво. Перший (відкритий) спосіб був найбільш простим, не вимагав особливих навичок і великих затрат праці – це збирання кременю безпосередньо на поверхні або в місцях його природних оголень (наприклад, осипів). Другий (закритий) спосіб видається найбільш складним, таким, що вимагає спеціальних знарядь, навичок, суттєвих затрат праці та, відповідно, більш складної суспільної організації. Цей спосіб має на увазі видобуток кременю глибоко в товщах його залягань, часто невидимих на поверхні. Але, гадаємо, цей спосіб себе виправдовував: видобувачі кременю отримували чудовий за своєю якістю матеріал для подальшої обробки, забезпечуючи сировиною не тільки свої внутрішні потреби, але й постачаючи близькі й віддалені громади, як споріднені, так і іноетнічні.

Ми виділили «близький» і «дальній» радіуси поширення отриманої сировини. У першому випадку мається на увазі самозабезпечення окремих громад сировиною й продуктами її обробки, необхідних для функціонування цих колективів. У другому ж випадку мова йде про цілеспрямоване масштабне виробництво (видобуток, обробка) не стільки для внутрішніх потреб, скільки з метою експорту або отриманої сировини, або готових виробів з неї.

Також в роботі поставлене питання про масове постачання регіонів, що не мають якісної сировини (Побужжя, Подніпров'я, Буго-Дніпровське межиріччя), кременем із прилеглого мікрорегіону в басейні р. Велика Вись на противагу пануючій думці про більш далекого "донора" – територію Волині.

Наявність в Кукутені-Трипільській спільності видобувних шахт, функціонування яких вимагало певних навичок і трудомістких операцій, спеціалізованих майстерень з обробки кременю, транспортування сировини й продуктів розщеплення на віддалені території стали основою для виділення в цій спільності общинного ремесла, пов'язаного з видобутком і обробкою кременю. Таким чином, питання, пов'язані із цим ремеслом, враховуючи його багатогранність, складність і масштаби, повинні стати одними з основних при комплексному вивченні економіки Трипілля.

Ключові слова: *енеоліт, Кукутені-Трипільська спільнота, кремінь, сировина, видобуток, поширення та обробка кременю*

Fig. 1. Scheme of the main silica-rich regions and some local deposits of chalcedonoliths in Ukraine by V.F. Petrun' (Petrun' 2004, p. 204, Fig. 1).

I - LIGHT GREEN SAND WITH ORTZAND LAYERS

II - LIGHT GREEN GLAUCONITE SAND; III - CENOMANIAN SANDSTONE

IV - FERRUGINOUS SAND WITH FLINT NODULES; V - CALLOVIAN DARK GRAY CLAY

Fig. 2. Geological section of the Kaniv flint deposit in Maryin Yar near Kaniv (by P.S. Shydlovskiy: *Shydlovskiy 2005, Fig. 1*).

Fig. 3. Flint deposits near the village of Bodaky on Volyn' (A). Flint concretion from Bodaky (B), Archaeological Museum of the Institute of Archaeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine).

Fig. 4. Flint deposits near the village of Neporotove on Dniester (foto by V.I. Usyk).

Fig. 5. Bila Gora flint mines near Studenytsya on Dniester. Plan of the cave №2 (by S.M. Bibikov: *Bibikov 1966, Fig. 2*).

Fig. 6. Flint deposits near the village of Korobchyne on Velyka Vys' river.

A – Flint concretions in one of the ravines in Korobchyne (Zaliznyak *et al.* 2013, p. 7, Fig. 3);

B – Flint concretion from Korobchyne (survey by L.V. Kulakovs'ka), Archaeological Museum of the Institute of Archaeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine);

C – Sectional drawing of the mine №1 in Korobchyne (by O.V. Tsvek: Tsvek 2012, Fig. 3).